

Figure 4C: Expression of systemin family members in tomato roots.

Non-shared letters indicate groups with statistically significant differences

(2-way ANOVA: $F_{19,80} = 245.5$, $P = 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$, $R^2_{adj.} = 0.98$; Tukey's HSD post-hoc test with $P_{adj.} < 0.05$).

